

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: OHANAEDU****FIRST NAME: JOSEPH****PROGRAM CODE: DILT****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: PROF. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software: (MS Word - Office 365 on Windows 10)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Writing a good academic essay Writing (EUCLID 2021, 7-10)
2. Structure of academic essays (EUCLID 2021, 9-10)
3. Efficient punctuation Techniques (EUCLID 2021, 15-23)
4. America Versus British English (EUCLID 2021, 25-27)
5. Plagiarism and Reference (EUCLID 2021, 11-37)

ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

I have taken time to go through the entire course content of Period One of ACA-401D. From my understanding, I can describe Period One as containing essential writing rudiments, comprehensively packaged to prepare students with the requisite foundational tools for effective English language communication through efficient academic writing.

Period One of ACA-401D opened my eyes to fully understand the following writing skills- the step-by-step processes of writing academic essays, the important academic tools necessary to convey the actual and intended meanings of a piece of academic writing, the essence of acknowledging other academic authors in one's academic essays and the variants and style guides in academic writings.

My Period One response paper will discuss the following from the ACA-401D coursepack: writing a good academic essay, the structures of academic essays, efficient punctuation techniques, and British Versus American English Languages. I will finally discuss the relevance of referencing and avoiding plagiarism in academic writing.

2) WRITING A GOOD ACADEMIC ESSAY

Academic essay writing is different from other informal forms of English writing works. This is because academic essays are scholarly research-based pieces of work that are fundamentally non-fictional, and their findings and reports are usually publishable for record and reference purposes (EUCLID 2021, 7).

After patiently studying the ACA-401D course pack, I realised that for a piece of writing to qualify as academic writing; it must contain all the necessary English Language ingredients that are common in other qualified types of academic writing, which include properly acknowledging and referencing other authors; prose register, deduction of hypothesis based on evidence, and the writer's personal ideas as his contribution to the subject of the research (EUCLID 2021, 7).

Good academic writing requires some mandatory basic steps to be achieved. Firstly, a potential author must design a workable roadmap for the task. This starts with the gathering of academic resources and ends with the final draft of the work. EUCLID 2021 recommends that researchers start early enough to plan and execute this task. This would give the author ample time to source and read through the various resource materials many times beforehand and equally give the author time to critique the reading materials and analyse them thoroughly through thinking (EUCLID 2021, 7-8).

There is no doubt that multiple readings of resource materials will lead to regularly amending the drafts of the work. However, the resultant effect is that, in the end, the author will emerge with more appropriate answers to the research questions. From the ACA-401D course pack, I discovered that to present appropriate answers to research questions, the author requires enough research to develop the thesis and the answers (EUCLID 2021, 8).

In addition to proper planning, starting research early and consulting widely and severally is good. The researcher needs to formulate a background of the study while doing the writing. He needs to identify and separate the information he already has about the subject matter from other information he requires to know. He also needs to tell him the truth if he has enough useful resources to confront the essay questions. The availability or otherwise of this useful information will determine if the author has the evidence to support his arguments on the topic (EUCLID 2021, 8-9).

Just like one can find some valuable scholarly writing materials from peer-reviewed online journals, the ACA-401D course pack also exposed me to the knowledge that, apart from the listed reading materials, one can also obtain valuable reading materials from the library by searching the catalogs and index of related topics and subjects (EUCLID 2021, 9).

I also need to state that one of the important things I have learned in the course of this Period One is that a creative mind and critical thinking are key to writing good academic essays. A researcher is expected to consult a range of academic materials from different authors. It must be noted that in most cases, some authors would have opposing

views about a particular subject matter. This is why the researcher should brainstorm and expand his scope of knowledge through expanded research to evaluate the different lines of arguments. This evaluation is critical in academic essay writing and will eventually help the researcher to open any narrow views that would strengthen his arguments thereby giving credence to his final conclusion on the subject matter (EUCLID 2021, 9).

3) THE STRUCTURE OF ACADEMIC ESSAYS

When an author has researched and gathered enough academic materials to pen down the results of his academic voyage, he would firstly ensure that he has developed his research questions and has credible answers to support his arguments. Further to the foregoing, the author is expected to lend his voice to the topic of the essay. This is perceived as his personal contribution to the academic discussion and it is a compulsory part of academic writing.

The next step is that the author must organise his work in a recognised and consistent essay writing format. By this, the author can easily convey or transmit the exact meanings of his ideas to his audience.

EUCLID 2021 gives an idea of what the structure of an academic essay should look like. It recommends that an academic essay should have three parts- introduction, body, and conclusion. This structural arrangement encourages effective flow and transmission of information, consistency in the presentation of the author's arguments, and ease of identification of the author's voice on the subject matter (EUCLID 2021, 10).

I understood from the ACA-401D course park that the introduction part should be brief and contain preliminary general and opening orientation sentences. There should also be leading answers to the research questions that summarise the main ideas in the academic essay (EUCLID 2021, 10).

Similarly, the ACA-401D course park teaches that the body of the academic essay should be arranged in paragraphs, each conveying particular ideas and information as the building blocks of the writer's respective arguments. This is because it is in the body of the essay that the writers develop their discussions and answer the research questions using the knowledge acquired, relevant information derived, and evidence to support their arguments from research materials (EUCLID 2021, 10).

When answering research questions with multiple parts, it is recommended to break the essay's body part into different sections arranged in specific paragraphs. Each of these paragraphed sections should treat only one particular part of the question. The beginning sentence of each section should address the main question, while subsequent sentences can further address the points already raised and provide relevant evidence from the research on the subject matter. It is important to note that the evidence must be properly analysed and their significance properly situated to provide some conclusions that support the writer's stand (EUCLID 2021, 10-11).

Finally, the concluding part of an academic paper represents an overview of the entire writing exercise. The recommendation by the EUCLID 2021 course park is that the concluding part of an essay should be arranged from a specific point of view to the general conclusion. The conclusion must also restate and summarise the answers to the main points of the research questions and present any foreseeable implications and useful directions to potential researchers (EUCLID 2021, 9).

4) EFFICIENT PUNCTUATION TECHNIQUES

Punctuations are writing tools used mainly to separate words, phrases, clauses, and sentences during academic essay writing. Efficient application of these punctuations helps convey the appropriate and intended thoughts of an author's academic work. This would, therefore, mean that inappropriate application of punctuation can mislead the innocent audience and convey the unintended ideas of the author.

The general rule, as advised in the ACA-401D course park, is that authors should use as little punctuation as possible and necessary when writing an essay, provided that intended thoughts or ideas contained in the sentences are retained and not reduced or hyped (EUCLID 2021, 10).

Punctuations include commas, apostrophes, brackets, colons, semicolons, full stops, question marks, exclamation and quotation marks, etc. Each of these has its peculiar usage in the written academic world. For instance, apostrophes are used to differentiate singular nouns from plural ones. Colons indicate that subsequent sub-clauses are logically dependent on the previous ones, while semi-colons connect two related parts of a sentence that can, on their own, stand independently (EUCLID 2021, 16-18).

It is also from EUCLID (2021, 19) that I got a clearer understanding of using a pair of commas in essay writing. According to the course park, a pair of commas can only be used to separate a pair of clauses when the subsequent clause does not explain the previous clause. Once the subsequent clause further explains the previous clause, the ACA-401D course park directs that it would be unnecessary to use a pair of commas (EUCLID 2021, 19).

5) AMERICAN VERSUS BRITISH ENGLISH

Britain and its former colony, the United States of America, are recognised as two native English-speaking countries in the world. Notwithstanding their perceived similarities in the use of the English Language, there have been some major differences. For instance, in both jurisdictions, some English words have different spellings, yet they are pronounced the same way and they have the same meanings (EUCLID 2021, 25).

In other cases, English words that have the same spellings are seen to have different or additional meanings in the two climes. There are situations where the same English

words of the same spellings are pronounced differently by the Americans and the British. (EUCLID 2021, 26-27).

Other noticeable differences seen in the two climes include the placement of punctuations like full-stop after a quotation and the application of collective nouns and plural adjectives (EUCLID 2021, 27).

Due to foregoing differences and other regional variations in the application of written English, the ACA-401D course park recommends that a well-written essay must maintain consistency in using either the American style or the British style of English writing (EUCLID 2021, 25).

6) PLAGIARISM AND REFERENCE

Citing the sources of information during academic writing plays two important roles in academia. Firstly, it is a way of honouring and acknowledging previous researchers' contributions to the field of study. Secondly, it protects the writer from the penalty of plagiarism, which is a serious academic offence (EUCLID 2021, 11, 34).

Plagiarism is an unethical and punishable academic offence of using someone's research product without giving credit to the author, meaning that the major essence of referencing is to forestall the penalty of plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 11, 34).

When writing an academic paper, it is very important that a researcher, after consulting various sources in search of credible information, adds his voice to the topic as his contribution to the field of study. This is how the writer also impacts some originality through his findings, analyses, and deductions in the ongoing academic discussion. While the researcher does the foregoing, he must not fail to give credit to his sources of information.

The ACA-401D course park teaches us some vital ways of preventing the offence of plagiarism, like the in-text citation, which is the style of citing an author and the page in parenthesis (EUCLID 2021, 35).

I also learned two other things from the ACA-401D course park: no matter how much a researcher tries to paraphrase another author's work, it is necessary to reference the authors just as one would do when directly quoting them. And that it is important to make a bibliography of all referenced authors (EUCLID 2021, 35-39).

7) CONCLUSION

Writing a good academic paper requires some fundamental knowledge of the art of writing. Due diligence is required from the time of gathering resource materials to ensure that only relevant and related materials in the field are collected. It is, therefore, expected that researchers consult widely. Online and offline libraries are of the essence and useful

in academic writing. Searches can be done from catalogs of texts, peer-reviewed journals, etc.

Good and timely planning is another important approach because starting early gives ample time to read over materials more than once and write and rewrite thesis questions and answers till a final perfect work is achieved.

The writer must use the appropriate punctuation for a written paper to be easily comprehensible to the target audience. Irregular punctuation would likely convey the unintended thoughts of the writer, hence misleading the audience.

Similarly, it is important to maintain a level of consistency in style. Mixing American English and British English in a piece of academic writing displays writing immaturity on the part of the writer.

Finally, the relevance of acknowledging previous authors of sources used in any research materials cannot be overemphasised. It cures the unethical, damaging offence of plagiarism,

I must mention that the ACA-401D course park is well-loaded with several pieces of information that will take me some time to master completely. The ACA-401D is like a handout that must accompany me daily on this journey till the end of my program.

Similarly, I must also mention that one of the foreseeable challenges researchers face is the cost of accessing valuable materials for research work. Most quality materials are paid for. They are getting more expensive for the student class.

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